

Mapping the Landscape of Service Robots in Hospitality: A Bibliometric Analysis

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Target conference topic: Assessing research impact on technological development and innovation in hospitality.

Abstract

In recent times, the sector of robotic hospitality has undergone considerable growth and diversification, positioning itself as one of the most relevant and rapidly expanding economic fields globally. As a result of its increasing significance, it is imperative to conduct an analysis and synthesis of the existing literature on this subject over the past years. To achieve this objective, this bibliometric analysis examines the publications indexed in the Web of Science bibliometric database on the topic of `service robots` within the `Hospitality, Leisure, Sport, and Tourism` categories. The study retrieved 111 publications through a search query conducted on March 8, 2023, with the time range of analysis limited to 2017-2023. After considering the findings and reviewing the extensive literature available, we have reached a point where we can now present our primary conclusions. Among all Web of Science categories, Hospitality, Leisure, Sport, and Tourism accounted for 5% of all publications and ranked eighth. The study identified Chinese funding agencies as the most frequent funding source, alongside institutions from the USA, UK, Bulgaria, Turkey, and Macau. Ivanov, S. and Seyitoglu, F. had the most individual contributions, with 9 and 5 articles, respectively. The International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management and the International Journal of Hospitality Management published the most articles, with 23 and 21, respectively. In addition to providing a bird's-eye view of the emerging field through a literature map, the study also aims to investigate the top ten most cited articles in the category with a focus on ethics versus impact. This study offers valuable insights into the current state of service robots in the hospitality industry and a foundation for future research.

Keywords: Service Robots, Hospitality, Bibliometric Analysis